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Ruptures of the Unspoken on the Self: Resonances of Trauma in a Kannada Folktale “A Story and A Song”

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Abstract:

This paper scrutinises “A Story and a Song,” a folktale from A.K. Ramanujan's anthology *A Flowering Tree and Other Oral Tales from India* (1997), to trace the earliest and colloquial expression of trauma in folklore. It analyses the narrative in the folktale to articulate and reflect on the theme of trauma through an interdisciplinary framework that integrates folklore, gender, and trauma theory. Examining the folktale through the lens of trauma establishes vital connections between the story and its cultural significance, as well as a deeper psychological understanding of the experiences it portrays.

Keywords: Trauma, Kannada folktales, repression, gender.

Folktales remain among the earliest oral links between the past and the present. They contain creative attempts at storytelling and cultural narratives that educate, entertain, and bind communities across generations. In the case of Kannada folktales, no theme is left unaddressed. Fantasy, adventure, love, adultery, betrayal, horror, the supernatural, and homosexuality find

articulation, even in passing references. As with all folktales, plot gains precedence over depth, and the plots are rarely elaborate: “The style is swift, the diction racy, dialectical. The narrative rarely digresses or elaborates” (A.K.Ramanujan, *Another Harmony* 45). They reflect the different spectrums of human experiences, as well as an inclusive dimension of assent and dissent, minority and majority, right and left, and margin and centre. The fluid nature of the tales suggests a dynamic storytelling tradition that transcends class, caste, and culture. The flexibility of the medium allows for revisions, deletions, and additions, contingent on the narrator. The mutable stories, subjected to the storyteller’s perspective, take different spins. Tellers of tales were not authoritative figures, as A.K.Ramanujan observes in the “Telling Tales” chapter of *Another Harmony* (4). The central storytellers of folktales are often women, and their only prop is their voice (46). Ramanujan draws a parallel between folktales and *akam* poetry, attributing the features to the interior or domestic narrative tradition, opposite to the *puram* category, the exterior or the public of the genre. “The language of the domestic tale is close to ordinary speech, heightened or lightened occasionally by the talent of the granny (45). *Akam* and *Puram* are two distinct poetic genres in Sangam literature that represent different aspects of human life.

Kannada folktales showcase the rich and the powerful in all their glory, yet cut them down to size, and elevate the poor and the underprivileged in social hierarchy, constantly reshuffling the dynamics of social mobility. Paradoxically, they often embody hierarchical, power-centred ideologies while simultaneously upholding ethical, individual endeavour-centric values, propelling ordinary people into greatness and great people into decline. This intersection of folktales, in particular, is both a simplistic and complex angle of cultural narratives. They distil intricate emotions into accessible narratives that resonate deeply with listeners.

The first folktale in A.K. Ramanujan's anthology of Kannada folktales, *A Flowering Tree and Other Oral Tales from India* (1997), “A Story and a Song,” encapsulates trauma in a concise form. The narrative unfolds as follows: A woman knows a song and a story. Instead of sharing them, she chooses to repress them. The purposeful choking of the story and the song results in internal conflict, and the harboured song and story become vindictive. In an unexpected turn of events, the story and the song transform and escape through her mouth when she is asleep. The story becomes a pair of shoes and sits outside her house. The song turns into a coat and hangs on a peg.

The strange objects, apparently belonging to another man, found in the house raise suspicions for the husband, who conjectures about his wife’s illicit affair. His unease prompts him to confront her with pointed questions regarding what transpired. While he demands an explanation, the wife pleads innocence. Following the conflict, the husband leaves home to sleep in the village temple. Exhausted by the outcomes, she extinguishes the lamp in her home and sleeps. The lamp from the woman’s house joins the usual everyday congregation of lamps at the temple late, and when asked about the reason for its late joining, it narrates in anecdotes to other lamps of the village, “The lady of our house knows a story and a song. She never tells the story and has never sung the song to anyone. The story and the song got suffocated inside, so they emerged and transformed into a coat and a pair of shoes. They took revenge, but the woman does not even know” (6). The husband, resting at the temple, overhears the conversation affirming his wife’s innocence. The unexpected revelation by the lamp in his house leads him to a new understanding. Returning home to probe more, he engages her to obtain clarification. The inquiries cause her more confusion and perplexity as she struggles to comprehend the situation. Having

forgotten about the song and the story inside her, she keeps repeating, “What story, what song?” (5).

A.K. Ramanujan categorised this folktale as a metastory evocative of the importance of storytelling in preserving cultural traditions that safeguard both community and individual health. The Kannada folktale, which A.K. Ramanujan interpreted as an exegesis of the dangers of stifling the act of storytelling, admonishes “niggardly non-tellers” about the cost of suffocating a story or a song (5). The text is fluid, open-ended, and as enigmatic as possible, inviting multiple readings. The lack of depth and detail that characterises most folktales leaves a lot to the reader's imagination. This meta-narrative also resonates profoundly with themes surrounding trauma and emotional expression.

The theme of trauma in fairy tales and folk tales is an interesting area of research. Modern studies delve into folktales and fairy tales to grapple with contemporary issues. Fairy tales like “The Twelve Brothers,” “The Singing Bone,” “Cinderella,” “Rapunzel,” and “Hansel and Gretel,” from *The Brothers Grimm collection* (1981), refer to the motif of suffering and trauma. Usually ending on the scheme ‘all is well that ends well,’ folktales do not engage with the motif of trauma directly. Reflecting on the medium of fairy tales as the one that deviates from reality, Jeana Jorgensen writes, “Fairy tales as magic mirrors that artistically distort reality rather than displaying it forthright are not perfect vehicles for reflecting the entirety of human experiences” (13). This opaqueness concerning the entirety of human experience offers a vast scope for studies in folktales.

Trauma is a relatively recent branch of study that directs the understanding of the psychological repercussions of difficult experiences, such as war, abuse, accidents, and natural disasters. In contrast, the folktales in A K Ramanujan’s collection date back to much earlier times. Trauma in modern literature and films is not a novelty but a recurrent and ubiquitous theme, “Dress

this story up or down: on the page and the screen, one plot - the trauma plot - has arrived to rule them all” (Sehgal par. 4). Trauma plots have almost reached the point of redundancy in contemporary fiction. However, the trend of locating the narration in trauma plots is thriving thanks to the horrific realities of war and disasters and the rise of awareness towards the psychological impacts of these realities in contemporary times. Modern fiction turns the narrative gaze toward the past, through flashbacks, to explore why the characters suffer. For example, the trauma of Krishan or Dinesh in Anuk Arudpragasam’s novels leads us through the excavation of the individual past of the characters, which often coincides with the past of their community or nation. War novels explore the trauma that war leaves behind in its characters, causing them to suffer profound emotional distress. The repeated recurrence of trauma theme in fiction makes Parul Sehgal question, “In a world infatuated with victimhood, has trauma emerged as a passport to status - our badge of courage?” (par. 6). Unlike the current scenario in literature, where trauma narratives are predominantly omnipresent, the present study aims to understand the articulation of trauma in folk narratives when both the tellers and listeners of folktales lacked the lexicon to describe it. The absence of terminology does not necessarily imply the absence of experiences of trauma. Therefore, the attempt here is to discern the concealed, under-the-surface experiences, drawing on psychological perspectives.

In exploring this theme further through its layers of meaning, “A Story and a Song” serves as an allegory for grappling with trauma. It is a short, illustrative text on trauma and its dimensions. The presence of the story and the song, both repressed, yet harboured in the woman, is unfathomable to her. The entities of the story and the song occupy a significant space in her body, yet she is unaware of it. Cathy Caruth calls trauma the “narrative of belated experience, far from telling of an escape from reality - the escape from a death, or its referential force - rather attests to

its endless impact on life” (*Unclaimed Experience* 7). The unconscious act of suffocating the story and the song proves disastrous to the woman, putting her reputation and family life at risk. The story, narrativising trauma, focuses on the challenging experiences and the transformed exigencies of experiences that return to affect the subject. This pivotal point of the folk tale is a metaphorical representation of what the woman had suppressed, which undergoes different transformations. The total unrelated nature of the suppressed experiences, where the woman thinks it is best to leave them unarticulated, gradually begins to harm her. It is not clear why the woman deals with it in silence. However, it is interesting to note that the woman did not process the bottled feelings in any way, which makes them unclaimed. The preferred mode of dealing with it for the woman was silence. The unregistered, unacknowledged, and unspoken nature of her experiences and emotions leads to unexpected manifestations. The voicelessness and agencylessness of the woman render her as the other, which she embodies within herself and struggles to navigate. The experience is close to her but unknown to her. The trapped emotions and experiences demand that she deal with them in some way or another. The frozen, stagnant quality that makes her stuck in time and space without acting out or working through sets her bodily responses to rebel against the stifling of emotions. The vengeful story and the song come back to her in complex ways. The coming or the return of the experiences establishes the crooked connection with her after she has refused to acknowledge them in the desired way. The suppression antagonises and dramatises the detached and disjointed angle to be forcefully seen, heard, and acknowledged. This aspect of the challenging experiences coming to haunt the subject later points to what Caruth referred to as “delayed appearance and belated address” (*Unclaimed Experience* 4).

This folktale unravels the affinity between the repression of experiences and their transmutations. It is possible to interpret the protagonist’s reluctance to confront the story and the

song as stemming from difficult or unassimilated experiences unknown to her, which precipitate internal conflict in the woman. The woman's silence is also a pointer to the intentional suppression of articulating or processing emotions, which later affects her well-being. Repressed experiences often find ways to resurface and compel expression. For example, repression creates an internal struggle between agency (the desire to speak out) and containment (the urge to remain silent). The experiences the survivor cannot leave behind resurface later and take strange manifestations.

Bessel van der Kolk reframed our understanding of trauma in *The Body Keeps the Score* (2014). He drew a parallel between the impact of trauma on the body and the mind. His clinical research demonstrates that the body retains information that the mind cannot fully process. His research highlights the reciprocal relationship between traumatic events and bodily responses. It underscores the intricately woven interplay between bodily responses to traumatic events and the emotional turmoil experienced within those contexts over time. He writes about dissociation in *The Body Keeps the Score* as “simultaneously knowing and not knowing” (123). The folktale “A Story and a Song” unravels the complexity of the mysterious mind. It can be one of the earliest takes on articulating trauma.

The symbolic role of the lamp in the folktale, which illuminates darkness, also quells confusion in the husband's mind. In Kannada folklore, the lamp serves as a fantastical medium to shed light on darkness, an agent of truth, or even a spiritual presence. In Devanoora Mahadeva's *Kusumabale*, the story begins with the gossip of the lamps or *Jothammas* (the house lamp spirits). The guardian-lamp spirits in Mahadeva's work are empathetic and driven by a strong sense of justice. In Girish Karnad's *Nagamandala*, the lamps (flames) take on the function of storytellers and sometimes even embody the agency of marginalised narratives. In the present folktale, the lamp symbolises knowledge and morphs into the medium through which the woman reveals her

experiences. It becomes a witness to the suffering, an external entity that can reason out with the help of the knowledge, which is incomplete, as the woman herself remains in the dark of her turmoil.

The trapped emotions demand acknowledgement, yet remain frozen in time due to her inability or unwillingness to confront them directly. Consequently, these repressed narratives return unexpectedly with heightened intensity after being denied recognition for so long that the act complicates their emergence into consciousness, forcing them into visibility despite initial resistance from herself. Following this “return of the repressed” phenomenon of Freud, Dominick LaCapra further builds on the idea of transference, which is a “more conscious summoning of the repressed”. Transference repeats or acts out a past event or relationship in a new, therapeutic setting, allowing for critical evaluation and change (Berger 576). The metaphorical nature of the folktale points to the intersection between knowing and unknowing, as Cathy Caruth expounds on ideas of latency, duality, and departure in “Freud, Moses and Monotheism” chapter in *Unclaimed Experience*. The period of forgetting in the context of the folktale is obscure. The woman remains unaware of it, even after the return of the repressed in the form of a coat and a pair of shoes, as Caruth says, “The site of trauma also opens up a new mode of seeing and listening” (56). The appearance of the symptoms, which is visible to the husband but not the woman after the “incubation period” (Freud), which is also termed “latency”, refers to the “fact that the victim of the crash [traumatic experiences] was never fully conscious during the accident itself (Caruth 17).

The suppression of the woman’s emotions, self-imposed or an imposition demanded by social stigmas, is akin to what the narrator in “The Yellow Wallpaper” suffers, subjected to isolation, barred from writing and forbidden to speak about her condition. She refers to writing as a “great relief” to her mind. Her husband and brother, both physicians, forbade her to do so, “I am

forbidden to ‘work’ until I am well again. I think it is a very good thing to write about one’s experiences, and I think that it is an excellent plan to do it in the form of a journal” (Gilman). The repression of the woman in the folktale is evident in the way she has alienated herself from the song and the story, which serve as metaphors for her intimate thoughts and experiences that she intentionally stifled. The self-repression in the folktale and the repression by an external person in "The Yellow Wallpaper" reflect in different ways. In the latter story, the narrator's husband prevents her from using her imagination and creative powers to make stories, deeming them dangerous, which may ‘excite her fancy’ (Gilman). The therapeutic effect of articulating one’s repressed emotions, which characters in both stories do not experience, comes at a cost. The coat and the pair of shoes are the physical testimony to the trauma, releasing the voice that a story and a song the woman had earlier muffled. In this way, the released song and the story find a voice through the rupture, or the wound (Caruth 2). Another Kannada folktale in A.K. Ramanujan's *Folktales from India*, “A Flowering Tree,” extends the physical metamorphosis of trauma, where the woman transforms herself into a flowering tree, then into a mutilated body, and finally into the healed self.

Hence, the folktale condenses key aspects of trauma in four ways: Firstly, the story brings the uncanniness of the woman’s experience to the fore. Secondly, the tale points out the return of the repressed aspect of trauma. The suppressed story and the song depart from her only to return in different, transformed forms. The self-mutating quality of the traumatic experience is evident in the transformed objects, establishing an encounter with the other or the other side of the silence’ (Urvashi Butalia). Lastly, it underscores the silence, obliviousness and agencylessness of the sufferer of trauma. The silence, in the context of the folktale, could have different connotations. It could be an inability to understand the complexity of experiences in the absence of external support

or the lack of tools to articulate female experiences in a phallogocentric language. Both hypotheses direct us towards the necessity of reinventing, relearning, speaking against, and speaking outside the specular phallogocentric structures of language (Shoshana Felman 10).

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